

Dissemination: Share confidently

Share & Disseminate

Determine Data Ownership and Intellectual Property

To effectively share data, researchers should first resolve any data ownership issues to confirm that they have approval to share the data. If researchers have questions, they should consult their PI, members of their department administration, or, if needed, the [Office of Technology Development](#).

- **[Intellectual Property Policy](#)**: The rights, those responsibilities, and principles that determine how research data should be handled ultimately belongs to the University.
- **[Research Data Ownership Policy](#)**: The University asserts ownership over research data for projects conducted at the University, under the auspices of the University, or with University resources. The University delegates stewardship of the data to PIs, therefore the PI has full responsibility for data management. Data ownership policies are available from the [Office of the Vice Provost for Research](#).

Review or Create Data Use Agreement(s)

A Data Use Agreement (DUA) is a binding contract between organizations that governs the transfer and use of data. It is an agreement between the data producer and secondary data user(s) and may impose rules for reuse, storage, re-dissemination, and disposal or termination. Find out more information about [initiating and processing DUAs](#).

- **[Incoming Data](#)**: When obtaining data from any third party (e.g., dbGaP, ICPRS). The appropriate Harvard office will help identify any additional special requirements that must be completed prior to accessing the data, as well as conditions for what to do with the data at the end of the project.
- **[Outgoing Data](#)**: When providing Harvard data to a third party, the Harvard sending party must prepare a DUA with input from appropriate Harvard offices. Data may be transmitted to the Data Recipient in accordance with the DUA terms and conditions.

Fulfill Data Sharing Requirement(s)

There may be requirements from funders and publishers to provide access to research data.

- **[Funder Data Sharing Policies](#)**: SPARC resource of current federal funding agency data sharing policies.
- **[Journal Data Sharing Policies](#)**: CHORUS resources indexing publisher data sharing policies.
 - Publishers have Data Availability Policies at the publisher level or at the journal level. Typically, authors must provide a Data Availability Statement published as part of the accepted article.

Apply Open Science Practices

Sharing all aspects of your research data and protocols is important for open and reproducible science. Here are some helpful resources to get started and practice open science:

- **[Open Access Publishing](#)**: The free unrestricted online access to scientific and scholarly research
 - Publish in an open access peer-reviewed journals (e.g., [Directory of Open Access Journals](#))
 - Deposit in an open access repository (e.g., [Digital Access to Scholarship at Harvard](#); [Preprint repositories](#))
- **[Open Materials and Methods](#)**: Open methods, protocols, and materials facilitate replication and reuse
 - **[Protocols](#)**: Sharing experimental methods and step-by-step protocols supports reproducibility
 - **[Reagents](#)**: Reagent repositories help support validating and sharing reagents

★ **[protocols.io](#) is a collaborative platform for publishing step-by-step methodologies**

The Countway Library offers protocols.io Premium for the HMS/HSDM/HSPH research community. Premium accounts expand access to private and secure workspaces, increased storage capacity, and dedicated support.